

“CONTEMPORARY GREEN HRM PRACTICES AT IT COMPANIES IN TRICHY.”

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Abstract

Green HRM is an emerging idea in HRM that aims to protect the environment while also enhancing the organization's reputation, in addition to the traditional HRM functions. Because businesspeople use a lot of resources from the environment and don't offer anything back to the ecosystem. As a result, it is the organization's responsibility to embrace green HRM for the sake of environmental sustainability. People are becoming more conscious of natural disasters and environmental challenges in order to provide remedial measures to society and the environment. Green HRM is critical in all sectors in order to decrease pollution and take steps to protect the environment. Hence in this research paper reveals that how Information Technologies companies are implementing green HR practices and what is the outcomes of its results.

Keywords: Green HRM, Environmental sustainability and natural calamities.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional human management places a premium on physical assets, and labourers are viewed as machine and material caretakers. People management has recently changed as a result of several stages, particularly after the Industrial Revolution. Trade unions were crucial in the early years of HRM development. Finally, firms recognise the critical role of employees in the success of their businesses and the expansion of wealth creation. It assists them in gaining a competitive advantage. Human assets add value to other assets by allowing organisations to shift their functions and develop new cultures. Incidentally, the organisation can achieve environmental sustainability by introducing green human resource management for managing human assets and it could pass through other physical assets of the organisation. Dumont et. al. revealed that green HRM directly and indirectly influenced in the green behaviours and green climate in the organisation.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

It is in the urge of emergency to make the organisation is environment friendly. For example, we are currently experiencing climate change and global warming as a result of environmental pollution and inadequate environmental resource management. It is the source

of the greatest environmental hazards to all species. Every year, the temperature rose by 2 to 3 degrees Celsius, while the sea level rose by 15 to 25 metres. To keep the temperature from rising above 1.5°C, we must reduce global greenhouse gas emissions by 7.6% every year between 2020 and 2030. In European Union cooling and heating systems devour more than 50 % of building energy and fossil fuels at a level of 84 % and 1.1 billion people countenance imminent threats from a lack of cooling. Air conditioning and refrigeration consuming energy and heat pump sectors expected to surge 33 times by 2100, to avoid cooling and heating emissions construct renewable energy and energy efficiency.

These issues have emerged as a result of the organization's lack of environmental management practises. As an outcome, in all sectors, aim to collaborate on environmental and human resource management in order to adopt Green HRM. HRM's operational activities, including as recruiting, training and development, motivation, performance, and compensation administration, are all connected with the preservation and conservation of natural resources. It contributes to the organization's sustainable use of natural resources. This paper discusses the green HRM practices among the employees of IT sectors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ✓ To Analysis the existing green HRM practices among the employees of selected Information Technologies Company.
- ✓ To provide suggestions for effective implementation of Green HRM.

METHODOLOGY

The primary and secondary data were used in this study. Primary data collected through the pre-tested questionnaire and secondary data collected from books, journal, articles and websites. Total population of the selected information technology companies are 260 employees. By using stratified random sampling technique 61 questionnaires were collected from the respondents. The collected were analysed by using frequency analysis, pearson correlation test, mean and standard deviation.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE: 1 INITIATIVE OF GREEN HRM PRACTICES IN THE ORGANISATION

S. No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percent
1	Below 1 year	17	27.9
2	1-5 years	23	37.7
3	5-10 years	10	16.4
4	Above 10 years	11	18.0
	Total	61	100.0

Source: Primary Dat

The above table shows that 37.7% of the organisations started their green HRM practices more than one year and less than five years. 27.9% of the organisations have been initiated the green HR practices less than one year. Notably, 18% of the IT companies have been practicing green HRM in their organisation for the last ten years. 16.4% of the organisations customized their HR practices to environment friendly for 5 to 10 years. By the virtue of amendment of Companies Act 2013 the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) becomes mandatory to the companies from April 2014. Hence, it's clear that 37% of the organisation practicing green HRM for last five year. In early 2000 the IT sectors were booming in India. In the initial times they had in a position to spend for establishments and infrastructural development, hence, they did not have sufficient fund for investing in green practices. Thus, the organizations practice green HRM for more than ten years is relatively low i.e18%.

TABLE: 2 THE TABLE SHOWING THE PEARSON CORRELATIONS AMONG THE FUNCTIONS OF GREEN HRM

		Overall satisfaction on Green HR initiatives.	Green procurement	E-training and development	E-compensation	Green performance appraisal indicators	Green grievances redressal mechanism	HR Data centre
Overall satisfaction on Green HR initiatives	Pearson Correlation	1	.590**	.589**	.569**	.632**	.494**	.460**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
Green procurement	Pearson Correlation	.590**	1	.704**	.619**	.662**	.532**	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
E-training and development	Pearson Correlation	.589**	.704**	1	.604**	.528**	.691**	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
E-compensation	Pearson Correlation	.569**	.619**	.604**	1	.532**	.645**	.720**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
Green performance appraisal indicators	Pearson Correlation	.632**	.662**	.528**	.532**	1	.612**	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
Green grievances redressal mechanism	Pearson Correlation	.494**	.532**	.691**	.645**	.612**	1	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
HR Data centre	Pearson Correlation	.460**	.621**	.623**	.720**	.579**	.657**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61	61

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Source

The table 2 shows that the correlation between various functions of green HRM initiatives in the selected companies and overall satisfaction of HR practitioners in the companies. Green procurement is the foremost function of personnel management. It involves adopting online application form, virtual interview and so on. It positively correlated with other components of functional green HRM.

E-training and development programmes such as Computer Based Training (CBT), through e-learning platforms, mimic class-room style training, visual contents with lectures' voice over, online reading materials, learning management system, mobile tools, content creation platforms and tools, and so on. These are positively corrected and proved the significance with other green HR initiatives.

E-compensation is another important initiative of the Green HRM practices in the IT companies. It includes both direct pay and indirect pay and other type of payments like base pay, commission, overtime pay, bonus, profit sharing, merit pay and other fringe benefits. The e-compensation systems implemented through employee information system, attendance record system, system for leave, emolument and PF details, generate pay slips, annual returns forms. Along with that the Flexible working hour, car-pooling and energy star qualified appliances are given as green rewards and recognition to the employees. The result revealed that the aforesaid e-compensation mechanisms have positive correlations with other components of green HR practices.

Green performance appraisal indicators articulate that green standard in performance evaluation is used to measure the environmental responsibilities of employees and Employees' involvement on environment. It is emphatically correlated with other factors green HRM practices in the Information and Technology sector.

In further, green grievances and redressal mechanism has positive association with all other Green HR practices. It demonstrates that using technology and online mechanism to avoid paper and other hard materials used and designed to improve transparency, openness of investigations.

Data centre is the heart of green HRM implementation and practice. It provides facilities like remote storage, data processing, data retrieval and distribution of large amount of data. The Pearson correlation analysis over again proved the significance with other green HR initiatives and constructive correlation.

The analysis revealed that the HR practitioners' satisfaction correlated with green procurement, e-training and development, e-compensation, green performance appraisal indicators, Green grievances redressal mechanism and HR data centre. And also it proved that these are significant for the overall satisfaction of Green HR initiatives undertaken by the HR practitioners.

FINDINGS:

- ❖ Majority of the IT companies are started to implement the green HRM practices for more than 5 years.
- ❖ Despite the fact that the IT industries do well in terms of Green HRM functions. Employees in IT firms require a green HR initiative awareness campaign.
- ❖ Adoption of Green HR practices lead to gain the competitive advantages in the eyes of the stakeholders and environment sustainability in corporate culture.

SUGGESTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF GREEN HRM

- Apart from the mandatory CSR activities the organisations should focus on green HRM implementation and try to achieve competitive advantage.
- Reduce paper usage in all the functions of HRM. Use the internet for procurement, specially customized software can be used for the training and development programmes, determining compensation, handing grievance and redressal mechanism and so on.
- Install green products all over the working place and encourage the employees to use.
- Recognise and reward the employees who immensely involved in environmentally friendly activities.
- Organize awareness programmes like competitions and cultural among the employees to make them more aware and grab their support to successful green HRM initiatives.
- The management should come forward to implement green HRM and available to motivate the employees in all terms to achieve environmental sustainability.

CONCLUSION

Organizations should strive for both economic growth and environmental sustainability. Wealth creation enables them to compete in today's market and also allows them to invest heavily in green practises within the firm and among stakeholders. It enhances their brand image while also attracting and retaining loyal customers and top personnel. It over again facilitates them to maximize their profit.

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